

Evaluating the Immediate Impact of Beaver Reintroduction

on Woodland Valley Farm

Opportunities for Habitat Creation • Conflict with Existing Land Use

1. Introduction

The Eurasian beaver (*Castor fiber*) is an ecosystem engineer whose dam-building alters riverine and floodplain systems by modifying hydrology and sediment dynamics, promoting wetland formation and associated ecosystem services (Wohl, 2019). As a result, beaver reintroductions are increasingly viewed as a nature-based solution for landscape restoration and climate adaptation across Europe (Yanuta et al., 2022). However, these benefits are often accompanied by potential conflicts in agricultural landscapes, particularly where inundation affects productive land uses such as pasture or arable fields (Puttock et al., 2017).

Woodland Valley Farm (WVF) represents a typical lowland agricultural landscape where beaver reintroduction offers both opportunities for habitat restoration and risks of land-use conflict. While beavers are currently enclosed within a managed area, the likelihood of future expansion necessitates an assessment of the immediate impacts that a wild release could have beyond the enclosure.

Spatially explicit models are increasingly used to anticipate both opportunities and conflicts associated with beaver reintroduction, allowing impacts to be evaluated before management intervention (Dennis et al., 2024). This study aims to evaluate the immediate impacts of a wild beaver release at WVF by modelling the spatial extent and likelihood of beaver-induced flooding and assessing how this intersects with existing land use.

A probabilistic modelling approach is adopted to incorporate uncertainty in elevation measurements and dam placement, producing a “fuzzy” floodplain rather than a single deterministic, boolean outcome to provide insight into how beaver expansion may reshape the landscape.

2. Methods

Elevation data were collected in the field using handheld GNSS receivers along north and south of a stream reach. Each sampling location recorded both elevation and associated measurement error. All spatial data were projected to the British National Grid (EPSG:27700).

A spatial modelling workflow was implemented in QGIS using the Processing Framework and GRASS GIS. Hypothetical dam locations were derived along the stream network, with each dam assigned an elevation and an assumed dam height of 0.5 m (Dennis et al., 2024). Sampled elevation points were joined to nearby 10 hypothetical dam locations using a nearest-neighbour approach as a sensitivity analysis.

To account for uncertainty in GNSS measurements, a **Monte Carlo simulation** was performed, whereby random elevation values were repeatedly drawn within the recorded error bounds for each sampling point (Metropolis and Ulam, 1949). For each iteration, the elevation difference between sampling locations and nearby dams was calculated to determine whether locations lay within the potential zone of inundation.

Dam influence was further weighted using an exponential distance-decay function, assuming maximal influence at the dam and declining to near zero at distances of 100 m from the channel. Probabilities of inundation were summarised using the maximum weighted influence for each

sampling location.

Interpolated probability surfaces were generated using a **bilinear spline interpolation**, and a probability threshold of 0.5 was applied to delineate potential beaver floodplain areas.

The model was run 100 times, and resulting raster outputs were aggregated to produce a **fuzzy floodplain** likelihood surface. Floodplain extents were vectorised and intersected with land-use data to quantify the distribution of impacts across woodland, pasture and wood-pasture classes.

3. Results

The aggregated floodplain likelihood surface reveals a spatially heterogeneous pattern of potential beaver-induced inundation. Areas of high likelihood are concentrated immediately adjacent to the stream channel, particularly in low-lying sections where valley morphology favours lateral water spread. Floodplain likelihood declines with increasing distance from the channel, producing diffuse northern and southern margins characterised by greater uncertainty associated with elevation error, interpolation, and distance-weighted dam influence.

Figure 1. Probabilistic beaver floodplain likelihood.

Aggregated beaver floodplain likelihood surface derived from 100 Monte Carlo model iterations. Raster values represent the proportion of model runs in which each cell exceeded a probability threshold of 0.5, indicating likelihood of inundation due to beaver damming. Yellow denotes core floodplain areas with high likelihood; darker margins reflect greater uncertainty.

Intersection of modelled floodplain extents with land-use data indicates that woodland areas are most consistently affected across Monte Carlo iterations, suggesting a high probability of wet

woodland creation following beaver expansion. In contrast, pasture and wood pasture exhibit greater variability in affected area, reflecting their location at the margins of the floodplain where small changes in inundation extent alter land-use impacts.

Figure 2. Intersection of beaver floodplain with land use.

Spatial intersection of modelled beaver floodplain extents with existing land-use categories. Woodland areas show consistent overlap across runs, while pasture exhibit greater variability, reflecting marginal floodplain positioning. Wood pasture displayed intermediate variability, consistent with its transitional ecological and management characteristics.

Distributions of affected land-use area indicate that beaver impacts span a range of plausible outcomes rather than a single deterministic value, reinforcing the need for probabilistic modelling in landscapes with inherently diffuse ecological boundaries (Austin and Smith, 1989).

4. Discussion

4.1 Meeting the study objective

This study successfully evaluated the immediate impacts of a hypothetical wild beaver release at Woodland Valley Farm by integrating field-collected elevation data with probabilistic spatial modelling. The resulting floodplain likelihood surface provides insight into where beaver-induced inundation is most likely to occur and how these areas intersect with existing land uses. By integrating GNSS-derived elevation data with Monte Carlo simulation and spatial interpolation, the model moves beyond deterministic predictions and offers a more realistic representation of potential landscape change.

Metric	Opportunity (Woodland) - m ²	Mixed (Wood Pasture) - m ²	Conflict (Pasture) - m ²	O vs C (m ²)
Mean	3386.19	1962.51	3117.38	268.81
Median	3392.21	1938.18	3109.62	279.96
Std Dev	34.44	51.86	114.73	119.95
Min	3291.01	1892.74	2595.43	-97.58
Max	3497.29	2147.21	3446.44	695.58
25th %ile	3376.12	1938.18	3072.37	239.30
75th %ile	3402.61	1965.44	3158.15	317.67

Figure 3. Table 1. Summary statistics describing the distribution of land-use impacts across Monte Carlo simulations.

4.2 Opportunities for habitat creation

The modelled floodplain overlaps substantially with woodland areas, indicating a strong potential for the creation of wet woodland and associated riparian habitats. Such habitats are widely recognised for their high biodiversity value, supporting amphibians, invertebrates, and hydrophilic plant communities. Increased water retention within these areas may also enhance ecosystem services such as carbon storage and attenuation of downstream flood peaks. Beaver-created wetlands are consistently associated with increased habitat heterogeneity and species richness across trophic levels, particularly in lowland agricultural systems (Law et al., 2017). From a restoration perspective, these outcomes represent clear opportunities aligned with contemporary rewilding and nature-based solutions agendas.

4.3 Potential conflict with existing land use

In contrast, the intersection of the floodplain with pasture and wood-pasture land uses highlights areas where beaver activity may conflict with agricultural productivity. Inundation of pasture could reduce grazing capacity and complicate farm operations, particularly if flooding occurs during key growing or grazing periods.

Agricultural conflict associated with beaver activity is most frequently linked to pasture flooding and waterlogging, though impacts are often spatially constrained and temporally variable (Puttock et al., 2017). The probabilistic nature of the results indicates that while some areas are consistently affected, others experience intermittent or marginal impacts, suggesting that conflict risk is spatially variable rather than uniform across the farm.

By framing land-use impacts as distributions rather than deterministic outcomes, this study provides a more nuanced basis for decision-making. Rather than defining fixed areas of impact, the results demonstrate that potential conflict and opportunity exist along a continuum of likelihoods. Areas with low but non-zero probabilities of inundation may warrant monitoring rather than immediate intervention, whereas consistently affected pasture areas could be prioritised for mitigation measures such as flow devices or targeted fencing.

Figure 4. Comparison and risk assessment of woodland (opportunity) and pasture (conflict) floodplain intersection areas across Monte Carlo simulations.

The scatter plot (left) shows individual simulations relative to equal opportunity and conflict, while the cumulative distribution (right) summarises the net balance (opportunity – conflict), highlighting the probabilistic dominance of opportunity while retaining the possibility of conflict-dominant scenarios.

4.4 Uncertainty, assumptions, and sensitivity

Several assumptions underpin the modelling approach. The assumed dam height of 0.5 m represents a reasonable average but may not capture the full variability of beaver dam construction. Sensitivity to dam height implies that even modest increases could substantially expand floodplain extent, amplifying both ecological benefits and land-use conflicts.

Sensitivity of floodplain extent to dam height has been highlighted as a key source of uncertainty in beaver impact models, reinforcing the need for scenario-based evaluation rather than single-value predictions (Dennis et al., 2024).

Similarly, the exponential distance-decay function imposes assumptions about how rapidly dams influence declines away from the channel, which may vary with valley morphology, soil permeability, and hydrological connectivity.

The number of Monte Carlo iterations also influences result stability. While 100 runs provide a useful approximation of floodplain likelihood, increasing the number of iterations would further reduce stochastic noise and improve convergence, particularly for marginal floodplain areas.

Effect of Monte Carlo iteration number on beaver floodplain likelihood

Figure 5. Effect of Monte Carlo iteration number on predicted beaver floodplain extent.

A single iteration produces a binary floodplain strongly influenced by stochastic elevation error, whereas increasing the number of iterations generates a probabilistic floodplain likelihood surface. At higher iteration counts (100), core inundation areas remain consistent while floodplain margins exhibit gradual probability decay, reflecting uncertainty in elevation and dam influence.

Figures 1, 2 & 4 demonstrate how increasing Monte Carlo iteration number stabilises predicted floodplain extent, enabling probabilistic mapping of beaver inundation that can be meaningfully intersected with land use to identify spatial patterns of opportunity and conflict.

4.5 Influence of sampling design

Predictions derived from spatial interpolation are inherently conditional on sampling design, with uncertainty increasing in areas distant from measured locations (Isaaks and Srivastava, 1989).

Thus, emphasising the importance of thoughtful sampling design in ecological modelling.

While Monte Carlo simulation effectively propagates measurement error, it cannot fully compensate for sparse spatial coverage. Denser or more spatially extensive sampling could improve confidence in predicted floodplain margins and reduce artefacts introduced by interpolation.

4.6 Implications for beaver management

Overall, the results suggest that beaver expansion at WVF is likely to generate substantial habitat creation benefits while also posing manageable, spatially constrained conflicts with agricultural land use. The probabilistic framework presented here supports adaptive management by identifying both core opportunity zones and areas where mitigation or compensation may be required. Such information is critical for balancing conservation objectives with farm-scale economic considerations.

5. Conclusion

At Woodland Valley Farm, most simulations favour ecological opportunity through woodland wetland creation, while conflict with pasture occurs in fewer scenarios. This indicates that beaver reintroduction is a low-risk, high-reward intervention. Probabilistic GIS modelling supports uncertainty-aware, evidence-based restoration planning and adaptive management (Wohl, 2019).

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